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Thin Layer Chromatography of Azine and Oxazine Dyes†

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PIETSCH and Meyer¹ employed tlc for the analysis of dyes, while Dobres and Moats² used ascending tlc for the analysis of some common dyes, but the tlc of azine and oxazine dyes has not been studied so far. We have, therefore, undertaken the present study which involves a simple and rapid method for the separation of impurities in eight azine dyes and six oxazine dyes by the ascending tlc technique.

Experimental

The azine dyes investigated are, Neutral Violet (NV), Neutral Red (NR), Azocarmine G (ACG), Azocarmine B (ACB), Wool Fast Blue GL (WFBGL), Magdala Red (MR), Indulin Water Soluble (IWS), and Nigrosin (NG) (C. I. nos. 50030, 50040, 50085, 50090, 50320, 50375, 50405 and 50420, respectively), and the oxazine dyes are, Capri Blue (CB), Solochrome Prune AS (SPAS), Gallamine Blue (GB), Celestine Blue (CLB), Meldola's Blue (MB), and Nile Blue (NB) (C.I. nos. 51015, 51040, 51045, 51050, 51175 and 51180, respectively). The samples NV, NR, ACG, CB, SPAS, GB, CLB and MB were of George T. Gurr; ACB, MR and IWS of Edward Gurr; NG and NB of Fluka; and WFBGL of Bayer.

† The work on azine dyes presented at the 69th. session of the Indian Science Congress, Mysore, January 3-7, 1982, and that on oxazine dyes at the 53rd. session of the National Academy of Sciences (India), Goa, October 27-29, 1983.

The solvents employed for developing the chromatograms were of reagent grade quality.

Glass plates of size 75 μ were coated (250 μ thickness) with silica gel (particle size : 75 μ , Acme Synthetic Chemicals), prepared by the addition of 30 g of the gel to 60 ml of water and shaking thoroughly. The plates were activated by heating in an oven at 120° for 30 min. Methanolic or ethanolic solutions (0.1%) of the dyes were used for spotting and the following solvent systems were used for developing the chromatograms (A to D for the azine dyes, and E to L for the oxazine dyes): (A) benzene-chloroform-ethanol (5 : 3 : 3), (B) benzene-isobutanol-isopropanol-acetic acid-water (8 : 4 : 4 : 3 : 1), (C) chloroform-ethyl acetate-acetic acid-water (4 : 4 : 4 : 1), (D) chloroform-n-propanol-isopropanol (10 : 7 : 3), (E) chloroform-isopropanol-ethanol-acetic acid (10 : 6 : 4 : 1), (F) chloroform-isopropanol-ethanol (5 : 3 : 2), (G) chloroform-n-butanol-ethanol (5 : 4 : 2), (H) methanol-acetic acid (1 : 1), (I) glacial acetic acid, (J) benzene-methanol-acetic acid (13 : 5 : 2), (K) acetone-acetic acid (1 : 1), and (L) acetic acid-benzene-methanol (5 : 3 : 2).

2 to 3 μ l of the dye sample was spotted on the activated silica gel plates and developed with suitable solvent systems. After development, the chromatograms were air-dried and the R_f values determined for the visible spots. Thereafter, the chromatograms were sprayed with 5% methanolic sulphuric acid to detect any further impurities present.

Results and Discussion

Azine dyes : Of the eight azine dyes studied, six dyes, viz. NV, NR, ACG, ACB, WFBGL and NR gave good separations. IWS separated to some extent, but NG could not be separated. Use of solvent systems containing a single solvent resulted in poor separations. Acidic solvent systems have, however, been found to be satisfactory. Solvent systems containing strong alkalis, like NaOH, yielded poor resolution and tailing-off of many compounds. Incorporation of varying amounts of ammonia in the above systems has not yielded satisfactory separation of the compounds, whereas, incorporation of acetic acid resulted in better separations. Incorporation of a small amount (0.5% v/v) of HCl in solvent system (A) produced excellent resolution.

NR separated as five spots with R_f values, 0.82 (intense pink, major dye), 0.77 (light pink), 0.88 (light orange-yellow), 0.20 (light pinkish violet), and 0 (very light yellow). NV gave somewhat similar results with slight changes in R_f values and an additional red spot of very light intensity with R_f value 0.58. WFBGL has been observed as a single spot in all the solvent systems studied which indicates that the dye is highly pure. ACG separated as four spots with R_f values, 0.25 (intense orange-red, major dye), 0.17 (light red), 0.10 (light red), and 0.9

(very light red). ACB separated as five spots with Rf values 0.20 (intense orange, major dye), 0.25 and 0.03 (very light red, almost invisible), 0.13 (light orange), and 0 (red). MR gave two spots and the Rf values are 0.2 (bright red, major dye), and 0.27 (light red). Although IWS separated into three spots with Rf values 0 (intense red), 0.18 (light brown), and 0.2 (light pink), the separation is not satisfactory as the major part of the dye did not move and tailing-off of the other two spots is observed. NG did not yield satisfactory results.

Good results are obtained by employing solvent systems (A) and (C) with NV, NR and WFBGL, and solvent systems (B) and (D) with ACG, ACB and MR. Acetic acid and water can be used for better resolution of the components. Tank saturation is necessary while using the solvents, benzene and chloroform. Examination of the chromatograms under uv light has not resulted in any changes in the observations, except that the spot observed with MR at Rf value 0.27 exhibits fluorescence which disappears slowly.

No further impurities are found by spraying the chromatograms with 5% methanolic sulphuric acid.

Oxazine dyes : Of the six oxazine dyes studied, except CB, the remaining five dyes showed single

spots only, thereby indicating that they are homogeneous. CB, however, showed four spots with Rf values 0.96 (pink), 0.84 (greenish blue, major dye), 0.25 (blue), and 0.1 (green) in solvent system (E). The same four spots are observed in the solvent systems (F) and (G) also.

SPAS, GB, CLB and MB gave reddish navy spots in the solvent system (H) with Rf values 0.088, 0.04, 0.14 and 0.088, respectively, while NB gave a blue spot with Rf value 0.94 in the solvent system (J). Although MB showed a neat single spot, it has been found to be unstable on heating with a solvent or on long standing of the solution.

The present study is useful for the purification of the azine and oxazine dyes, which has been successfully achieved on a preparative scale.

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